

The effect of different priors on a discrete cosine transformation based EIT algorithm

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Abstract: Prior information, both morphological and functional, can improve reconstruction of the electrical impedance tomography (EIT). In this contribution, two different priors from a personalized morphological image were introduced into an EIT algorithm using discrete cosine transformation constraining subset. A retrospective patient research was conducted to demonstrate the effect that the different levels of priors have on the results. If the accuracy of the priors can be ensured, this algorithm can mean a step out for the possibility of a more interpretive EIT reconstruction facilitating the diagnostic, monitoring and automated adjustment of ventilator setting procedure in a clinical setting.

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I. Introduction

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is used to visualize the regional lung ventilation and aeration distribution from current induced voltage changes through the electrodes attached on the surface of the chest[1]. This technique has proven useful to reduce ventilator induced lung injury (VILI)[2] and to provide guidance to set adequate positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) levels for mechanically ventilated patients in the intensive care unit (ICU)[1]. However, in practice, EIT images are difficult to interpret. Low spatial resolution, blurred anatomical alignment, and reconstruction induced artefacts hinder the interpretation of the patient status in clinical settings. Introducing priors, e.g. structural information, into EIT images will be helpful for clinicians in forming a more direct, comprehensive insight, and might eventually facilitate the automatic ventilator settings.

Priors can vary, but are usually based on previous empirical studies of the tissue conductivities, the anatomical constraints or both. The prior information based on the different tissue properties can be incorporated in different ways, e.g. as grouped elements in a finite element model (FEM)[3]. Another approach to include the priors is to introduce a subset of basic functions to constrain the reconstruction, e.g. subspace regularization method based on the physiological information within the body[4].

As for a more personalized and more patient-specific prior, Schullcke et al. proposed an EIT algorithm with the prior as a subset of basic functions derived from morphological imaging approaches, e.g., CT. The generation of the constraining subset was proposed using the discrete cosine transformation (DCT) of the patient-related morphological images[5].

Even though the embedded personalized prior has been shown to improve the interpretability of EIT images, it comes with the same problem as all priors always induce: results are just as good as the validity of prior assumptions. For example, the DCT methodology might not be valid considering the fact that the status of the patient is changing over time, which should be evaluated.

The objective of this contribution is to evaluate the effect of simple and complex structural priors implemented in the DCT-based EIT algorithm. The evaluation was conducted over a retrospective patient dataset.

II. Method

II.1. DCT-based EIT reconstruction

The classical approach for reconstruction of conductivity distribution $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ in difference EIT is presented in equation (1) where vector $\mathbf{x} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{baseline}}$ is the change in internal conductivity distribution $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}^{\text{baseline}}$ is a vector containing the differences of measured voltage \mathbf{v} :

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J} + \lambda^2 \mathbf{R})^{-1} \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{y} \quad (1)$$

the matrix \mathbf{B} is the reconstruction matrix which calculates the impedance distribution variation from the measured boundary voltages. The jacobian \mathbf{J} is depending on the choice of $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\text{baseline}}$, which is usually not know, and on the shape of the domain. \mathbf{R} is a regularization matrix which have several options, e.g., $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}$ for Tikhonov approach, and λ is the weight of the regularization.

In the DCT-based EIT approach we replace the Jacobian \mathbf{J} with $\mathbf{J}_{\text{DCT}} = \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{K}$, where each column \mathbf{k}_i of \mathbf{K} is obtained by element-wise multiplication of the FEM-elements which are considered as lung tissue and basis vectors of a personalized structural image DCT as:

$$\mathbf{k}_i = \mathbf{T}(P_{m,n}, \alpha_p \alpha_q \cos \frac{(2m+1)p\pi}{2M} \cos \frac{(2n+1)q\pi}{2N}) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{T} is a mapping function assigning each pixel of the structural lung image $P_{m,n}$ to the FEM elements.

II.II. Patient data

The retrospective pneumonia patient data was recorded with a PulmoVista500 (Dräger Medical, Lübeck, Germany). The study was approved by the Human Investigation Review Board University of Szeged (approval number 67/2020-SZTE). The trial was registered on ClinicalTrials.gov under NCT04360837. The patient was deep sedated, intubated and ventilated with a PEEP step maneuver. The study period was seven days. Data were collected at 5th inter-costal space. The corresponding CT dataset at the first day of the ICU admission was used to obtain the shape of the lungs and the thorax as shown in Fig.1. The dorsal part of the left lung was shown as atelectasis.

The DCT-based EIT algorithm was implemented on the patient data, but with different prior information namely lung contour and lung detail, as in Fig.1. A difference image of ventilation distribution (Δ ventilation) was created from the reconstruction at PEEP 25 cmH₂O and at PEEP 10 cmH₂O on day 1, day 3 and day 7 respectively. In functional EIT analysis scope, Δ ventilation image between different PEEP levels is used to determine the potential recruitment and the possible overdistention during the PEEP trial[1].

Figure 1: The segmentation of the personalized lung priors and thorax shape from the corresponding patient CT.

III. Results and discussion

The difference image of ventilation distribution from PEEP 10 cmH₂O (lowest PEEP) to PEEP 25 cmH₂O (highest PEEP) of the subject is depicted in Fig. 2. In either reconstruction, a trend of decreasing potential recruitment (the light area in the lung shown in Fig. 2) from day 1 to day 7 can be observed, though with two different priors. In addition, a possible overdistention can be witnessed at the right ventral area in both the reconstructions on day 1 (the dark area shown on day 1, the first column in Fig. 2). However, a decrease of the impedance was observed in both dorsal part of the lungs on day 3 and day 7 in the reconstructions with only lung contour prior (the dark area in the first row in Fig. 2), whereas the decrease was not observed in the reconstruction using detail prior. Instead, little change is observed at the left dorsal part in the reconstruction using detail prior, where the CT image indicates atelectasis. However, the change of the atelectasis area cannot be verified due to the lack of CT images.

In general, regardless of priors, the DCT approach presents a more direct comprehensive and interpretable result. In

this contribution the deteriorating patient status in terms of the decreasing recruitment potential can be observed in reconstructions with either prior. However, the nature of the priors influenced the final results which is associated the risk of misleading interpretation if the priors are old or wrong, e.g. morphological changes occurred between CT examination and EIT measurement. Compared with the lung detail prior, the lung contour prior have less constrains over internal structures and boundaries, which might allow pathophysiological variations in a developing course of the disease. The integrated priors should be updated over time with predicting potential changes based on pathology and available patient measurements.

Figure 2: The difference image of ventilation distribution from PEEP 10 to 25 cmH₂O of the patient. Upper row: result from lung contour prior; Lower row: result from lung detail prior

IV. Conclusions

The reconstruction of the DCT-based EIT algorithm is attractive in terms of increasing interpretability and easy access to the image information. If the prior is confirmed correct and updated, this novel algorithm might proof helpful in a personalized protective ventilation treatment.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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